

D3.6

MPC implementation for hybridGEOTABS buildings

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Summary

The development of Model Predictive Controls (MPC) for hybridGEOTABS buildings is the main topic of Work Package 3 of the hybridGEOTABS project. The previous WP3 deliverables document various aspects of the research and development of white-box and/or grey-box MPC's, going from the development of a semi-automated toolchain for the development of an MPC (D3.1), the formulation of objective functions (D3.2), the MPC start-up strategies (D3.3), adaptive MPC (D3.4) and robust MPC (D3.5).

This deliverable (D3.6) documents the software and hardware implementation of the MPC's in the demonstration buildings. First, the MPC construction and the framework for the practical implementation are explained, for white-box MPC (by KU Leuven) and grey-box MPC (by Energoklastr) approaches. Then, the particularities of the implementation of the MPCs in the demonstration buildings is discussed, including a description of the control variables. Finally, the first observations of the behaviour and performance of the MPC are discussed.

Model Predictive Controls are implemented in real-life in four hybridGEOTABS buildings: the Infrac/Fluvius office building (white-box), Ter Potterie elderly home (white-box), Libeznice school (grey-box) and Solarwind office building (white-box). While this deliverable focuses on the MPC implementations, the documentation and performance assessment of the buildings with original and new controls is to be found in WP4: documentation of the building design, HVAC and control (D4.10-D4.11), white-box emulator models of the buildings (D4.7), measurement protocol (D4.4) and the performance assessment of the buildings and controls using simulated data (D4.9) and real-life data (D4.12-D5.2).

Finally, this deliverable documents the MPC development for one additional building, that is the Nathan headquarters building. Unlike the four aforementioned buildings, this building is not a real-life demonstration building in WP4¹. This building is the last building for which an MPC is developed in context of this project, making use of all the tools and progress made in developing white-box MPC during this and related projects at KU Leuven, and applying them to a building completely 'new' or 'unknown' to the MPC developers. Therefore, this control design exercise allows to assess the time and efforts needed to develop a white-box MPC. This deliverable D3.6 documents the MPC design and simulation results. The assessment of the design process and efforts is discussed in D3.3.

In this project, five MPCs have been successfully developed. The MPCs of the Infrac/Fluvius, the Ter Potterie, and the Libeznice buildings are currently controlling the buildings, each saving energy and improving the comfort. MPC of the Solarwind building has been tested extensively in simulations and it is currently deployed. Finally, MPC of the Nathan headquarters has been tested extensively in simulations and the deployment will be discussed with the building owner after this project.

During this project and in parallel to other KU Leuven projects the white-box toolchain has been largely extended, making it possible to develop accurate non-linear white-box MPCs based on models with more than 1000 states and hundreds of optimization variables while keeping the development time to a few days (see D3.3). Those MPCs proved to produce accurate results both in simulations and in real life operations. The grey-box framework was also extended to include ventilation and not only TABS and the robustness of the control was shown by its continuous operation throughout the entire project.

¹ the MPC in the Nathan building is designed and tested in simulations, but not implemented in real-life, nor assessed in WP4

Beside the MPC toolchain, KU Leuven developed its own framework for the communication between MPC and the machines during this project. It is based on the open-source python library *bacpypes*² for the BACnet communication and on cronjobs in a Linux environment to schedule and perform the different tasks. EK used instead the commercial software Mervis and its convenient API.

While the different MPCs are stable and rarely fail to converge, the MPC ON-time is still rather low for the white-box MPCs. This is due to a multitude of IT, BACnet communication, and hardware problems as described in the sections below as well as the high number of variables controlled by MPC. While some problems are unavoidable and are typical to aging buildings, more development is necessary to improve the robustness of the framework.

² <https://github.com/JoelBender/bacpypes>

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Nomenclature

Acronyms

AHU	Air Handling Unit
BMS	Building Management System
COV	Change Of Value
MPC	Model Predictive Control
RBC	Rule Based Control
VAV	Variable Air Volume

1. Introduction

The development of Model Predictive Controls (MPC) for hybridGEOTABS buildings is the main topic of Work Package 3 of the hybridGEOTABS project. The previous WP3 deliverables document various aspects of the research and development of white-box and/or grey-box MPC's, going from the development of a semi-automated toolchain for the development of an MPC (D3.1), the formulation of objective functions (D3.2), the MPC start-up strategies (D3.3), adaptive MPC (D3.4) and robust MPC (D3.5).

This deliverable (D3.6) documents the software and hardware implementation of the MPC's in the demonstration buildings. First, the MPC construction and the framework for the practical implementation are explained, for white-box MPC (chapter 2) and grey-box MPC (chapter 3) approaches. Then in chapters 4-5-6-7, the particularities of the implementation of the MPCs in the demonstration buildings are discussed, including a description of the control variables. Finally, the first observations of the behaviour and performance of the MPC are discussed.

Model Predictive Controls are implemented in real-life in four hybridGEOTABS buildings: the Infrac/Fluvius office building (white-box), Ter Potterie elderly home (white-box), Libeznice school (grey-box) and Solarwind office building (white-box). While this deliverable focuses on the MPC implementations, the documentation and performance assessment of the buildings with original and new controls is to be found in WP4: documentation of the building design, HVAC and control (D4.10-D4.11), white-box emulator models of the buildings (D4.7), measurement protocol (D4.4) and the performance assessment of the buildings and controls using simulated data (D4.9) and real-life data (D4.12-D5.2).

Finally, this deliverable documents the MPC development for one additional building, that is the Nathan headquarters building (chapter 8). Unlike the four aforementioned buildings, this building is not a real-life demonstration building in WP4³. This building is the last building for which an MPC is developed in context of this project, making use of all the tools and progress made in developing white-box MPC during this and related projects at KU Leuven, and applying them to a building completely 'new' or 'unknown' to the MPC developers. Therefore, this control design exercise allows to assess the time and efforts needed to develop a white-box MPC. This deliverable D3.6 documents the MPC design and simulation results. The assessment of the design process and efforts is discussed in D3.3.

³ the MPC in the Nathan building is designed and tested in simulations, but not implemented in real-life, nor assessed in WP4

2. White-box MPC framework

2.1. MPC framework

D3.1 describes the original MPC framework for white-box MPC. For the Infrac/Fluvius and Ter Potterie buildings, we have used a tool developed in parallel with this project and built upon the linearization methodology described in D3.1: the TACO framework; a Toolchain for Automated Control and Optimization [1]. TACO is a toolchain that generates optimization code from a Modelica model implemented using a Modelica library such as IDEAS [2]. TACO is used to automatically separate the equations of the Modelica model into three main parts: the equations which are independent of the states of the model and which can be pre-computed, the linearized equations of the building envelope, and the non-linear equations of the HVAC, as described by Figure 2-1.

Figure 2-1: Split up of the equation of the building model performed by TACO [3]

Each block can be solved separately using the most appropriate method which allows the user to solve non-linear optimization problems of more than 1000 states (originating from the building envelope) within acceptable optimization time. Finally, TACO creates an executable that computes the optimal solution of the optimization problem for the given inputs. For more details about TACO we refer the reader to [1].

The building models used by TACO are those described in D4.7 which make use of the open-source Modelica library IDEAS [2]. However, a few HVAC models needed to be adapted in order to be twice differentiable as requested by TACO.

2.2. MPC practical set-up

The practical set-up of Fluvius and Ter Potterie is given by Figure 2-2: the building and its HVAC system are controlled by one or several PLCs containing the original Building Management System (BMS). The BMS can be consulted through the local computer installed in the building. The PLCs have a BACnet over IP interface giving access to the read and write variables of the system (e.g. temperature from sensors, control signal for valve opening, etc.). The MPC computer contains the optimization code. It can interact with the BMS using the BACnet over IP network and retrieves or sends information from the internet (weather forecast using darksky.net, measurement data to database using kb.mervis.info, MPC meta data using Podio.com, etc.). The MPC computer does not need to be in the same building as long as it has accessed to the BACnet over IP network but it should offer remote access such that it can be maintained.

Figure 2-2: MPC practical set-up

2.2.1. MPC computer

The MPC computer performs the following tasks using cron jobs:

1. Every 30 minutes: fetch the weather forecast of the coming 6 days
2. Every 1 minute: read all measurement data from BACnet which is necessary for the observer (used for the MPC feedback) and for the post-processing. The post-processing is for example a PI controller tracking a set-point computed by MPC by controlling the actual control signal.
Remark: this cronjob is now being replaced by the Change Of Value (COV) method of BACnet which sends an update of the variable value each time the changes is larger than a given threshold.
3. Every 1 minute: restart the postprocessing controller if it is no longer running, and report an error if this is the case
4. Every 15 minutes: re-compute the MPC optimization and save the set points or control actions for the entire MPC horizon

Besides these actions strictly related to MPC, the MPC computer contains a few fallback mechanisms that disable MPC and reset the MPC BACnet priority such that the original BMS takes over:

1. the health of the connection between the MPC computer and the building is checked by means of a watchdog running both on the local computer and on the MPC computer. If the watchdog communication fails, MPC is disabled
2. MPC can be turned on and off from a web platform (Podio.com). The MPC computer regularly fetches the MPC status from the platform. MPC is disabled if Podio cannot be reached for more than 600s
3. Important equipment failure such as AHU or Heat Pump failure are also checked and MPC is disabled when that occurs.

Finally, measurement data are pushed to an online database (scada.mervis.info) every 5 minutes and any errors from the cronjobs are pushed to the online platform Podio.com with optional sms notification.

2.2.2. BACnet communication

The communication between the BMS and the MPC computer is possible using the BACnet over IP network. While the installed BMS hardware (Blue ID controller by Priva) is not BACnet native, it provides a BACnet router giving access to most inputs and outputs of the controller as well as its parameters but not to its internal variables. Example: the measurement input and control output of a PID controller are available on BACnet but not the set-point as it is an internal variable. Luckily, this is overcome by writing the min and max parameters of the set-point to the desired set-point value.

The BACnet protocol allows 16 priority levels. The MPC computer writes on priority 14, which is higher than the priority used by the original BMS, and thereby overrules it. The original BMS continues to work even when MPC is ON allowing to automatically fall back on it by resetting priority 14. The watchdog signals are written on priority 13 such that the reset does not affect it.

We developed our BACnet scripts using *BACpypes*⁴, a python library to build BACnet application. The scripts are used to get the list of BACnet objects and to read and write on those objects.

2.2.3. XML layer

Specific for the Solarwind building, an additional XML layer is added between the MPC computer and the BACnet communication system. This serves as an interface, only allowing access to the relevant BACnet points while adding an additional range limit check on control variables before being sent to the building. The XML files are communicated via an FTP server on the MPC computer.

Input and measurement data is pushed by the BMS to the server every 3 minutes. On the MPC computer, files are parsed to match the structure needed for the MPC algorithm.

To enable MPC control, an XML file with control variables, based on the MPC algorithm, is generated every 5 minutes. This file is checked to match the prescribed XML schema and sent to the FTP server if it passes. After downloading the file from the server, control variables are checked (again) to be in agreed range limits and are written to BACnet on a higher priority as RBC by the BMS. This further allows the control company to keep a history of the MPC control actions.

To disable MPC control, a reset frame is sent. This works twofold: for points with a BACnet priority table, the value on the higher MPC priority is removed, making the RBC controller on lower priority active. For points

⁴ <https://github.com/JoelBender/bacpypes>

without priority, the default value is written on BACnet. The needed behavior for each point and its default value are listed in an agreed XML watchdog file.

We developed the XML interface in python, based on standard XML python libraries.

3. Grey-box MPC framework

The grey-box MPC framework described in the following paragraphs differs from the white-box in two main aspects:

- MPC calculation is deployed as a cloud service (installed on a VPS server) and the setpoint are communicated to the building,
- grey-box models are used instead of detailed white-box equations.

The diagram of the HVAC system, controllers and user interactions is shown in Figure 3-1. Note that the scheme describes the real setup in demo building Libeznice. For other buildings, the connections within the building may differ (number of PLCs that control the HVAC technology and communication protocol between PLCs). The remainder has the same scheme:

- communication between Main PLC over proprietary Mervis protocol with SCADA system Mervis. This communication is secured, does not require any public IP addresses and can be tunneled through several proxies. The data are exchanged not only because of monitoring and historical data collecting, but also for communication of the user and MPC defined setpoint to the main PLC (main PLC then distributes the setpoint on the remainder of PLCs).
- Any computer or tablet can connect through web interface to the SCADA system. After authentication, user can see
 - the current values of the measurements, PLC variables and alarms.
 - historical trends for the all variables listed above
 - schemes of the technology
- MPC algorithm communicates over Mervis REST API with SCADA system
 - SCADA system provides current measurements and operational regimes of the building, setpoints for room temperatures and weather forecast
 - After computation of MPC task, the optimal setpoints are communicated back to SCADA system, which transfers them to PLCs in building.

Figure 3-1: grey-box MPC framework - Libeznice case

MPC code is composed of three main components

- Data preprocessing: optimization tasks are in general quite sensitive to high quality of input data. Preprocessing handles typical problems with quality of input data for MPC (frozen value, value out of typical range, last sample for a variable too old – new sample has not arrived, filtering, etc.). Since the grey-box framework leads to centralized MPC (i.e. one MPC for whole building), one wrong measurement may destroy all outputs from the MPC, therefore special care of the operational data is needed. Preprocessing is also carried out on solar irradiation forecast: SCADA Mervis provides forecast of global solar radiation on the horizontal surface (source NOAA) and preprocessing algorithm calculates the solar radiation on each façade.
- MPC calculation: once all data are prepared, the MPC task is executed. Within grey-box MPC framework, the MPC is implemented within CVXOPT optimization framework with ECOS solver.
- Preprocessing of the MPC output translates heat-fluxes on temperature setpoint, in the case of demo building Libeznice, it is described in deliverable report 4.10.

All MPC steps are calculated every 20 minutes.

4. Infrac/Fluvius

This section discusses the practical MPC implementation for Infrac/Fluvius. Section 4.1 lists the MPC optimization variables and the control variables sent to the BMS of the building, Section 4.2 describes the objective, horizon and constraints of the MPC and Section 4.3 gives some preliminary MPC results.

4.1. MPC control signals

The optimization variables of MPC and the actual control signals sent to the BMS are summarized in Table 4-1. For the convenience of the reader, the hydraulic scheme included in D4.7 is repeated here (Figure 4-1).

General remark: The current white-box MPCs are formulated as a non-linear but continuous optimization problem. Therefore, the optimization of on/off components is approximated by using a continuous signal in MPC and by applying a post-processing afterwards. Further development of TACO will allow direct mixed integer programming to optimize on/off control actions.

Figure 4-1: Fluvius: simplified hydraulic scheme

Table 4-1: Fluvius: MPC control signals in model and actual control signals to the Building Management System

	Optimization variables in model	Actual control signals to BMS	Remarks
AHU	Three-way valve opening heating coil	Supply ventilation set point	-
	Three-way valve opening cooling coil		-
	Modulation heat recovery wheel		-
	Pressure head supply fan	Pressure head supply fan	-
	Pressure head return fan	Pressure head return fan	-
Vent	Three-way valve opening re-heating coils	Postprocessing: PI controlling valve opening to track supply air temperature from MPC	21 re-heating coils. Some re-heating coils do not measure the supply air temperature. The zone temperature is then used instead.
	Opening VAV supply and return	Opening VAV supply and return	2x14 VAVs + 1 VAV. The same signals is sent to the supply and return VAV.
HYDRO	Two-way valves opening for each TABS circuits	Two-way valves opening for each TABS circuits	1 for each floor, so 4 in total
	Three-way valve to mix supply and return TABS	Postprocessing: PI controlling valve opening to track supply water temperature from MPC	-
	Two-way valves to switch between cooling and heating for TABS	Postprocessing: on/off	MPC assumes modulating valves while they are actually on/off valves
	Heat pump modulation rate	Temperature set point for heat pump	MPC assumes a modulating heat pump while in reality two heat pumps with each two non-modulating compressors are installed.
	Modulation of each circulation pump of borefield	MPC signal not used. RBC controls it	
	Modulation of circulation pumps for secondary side of heat pump, primary side of heat exchanger for cooling TABS and ventilation	Postprocessing: pump turned on if thermal power of circuit connected to it is higher than 5% of nominal power	3 pumps
	Modulation of circulation pumps of AHU: for heat exchanger for pre-heating coil, heat exchanger for the coiling coil, heat exchanger for heating coil	MPC signal not used. RBC controls it	3 pumps
SUM	# optimization variables: 49	# BACnet points: 147	

The Modelica model contains a detailed model of the Air Handling Unit (AHU) including the fans, recovery unit, heating and cooling coils. As the BMS already contained a well working control (after some manual tuning improvements) to track a set point supply ventilation temperature, we decided to let MPC control the set point instead of controlling each component. No loss of optimality is expected by this simplification. However, the supply and return fan pressure heads are directly controlled by MPC. While in RBC mode the pressure heads are kept constant during the day around 120 (return) and 200 (supply) Pa, MPC will lower it down to 30 Pa.

The ventilation system of Fluvius is further equipped with 21 re-heating coils and $2 \times 14 + 1$ VAVs to adapt the supply air temperature and the air flow per zone. While MPC optimizes the opening of the three-way valve of the re-heating coils in its model, the actual control signals sent to the re-heating coils are the air supply set point temperature. In the case where the re-heating coils do not measure it, a zone set point is used instead. VAV opening signals are controlled directly by MPC.

MPC also controls the hydraulic part of the HVAC. The opening of the two-way valves of the four TABS circuits is directly controlled by MPC. For the three-way valve which mixes supply and return water of TABS, a temperature set point is used instead as control variable. The control of the two-way valves to switch between cooling and heating for TABS are optimized directly. The resulting heat flow rates are used to decide which of the two-way valves is opened in practice.

The control of the different compressors of the heat pumps and of the borefield pump is a delicate task as a lack (or a delay) of flow to the heat pump will trigger an error and shut down the heat pump (which can then only be manually restarted). In this project we decided to leave those control variables to the BMS and to only control the heat pump set point temperature.

Finally, Table 4-1 indicates which circulation pumps are currently controlled by MPC and how the post-processing is done from the continuous MPC variable to the on/off control of the actual pump.

The total number of optimization variables is 49 while 147 control signals are sent to the BMS. The difference comes from the post-processing and from the fact some set points can only be indirectly controlled (e.g. PI set point can only be controlled by overwriting its min and max value).

4.2. MPC objective, horizon, and constraints

The MPC objective considers the energy use of production and distribution devices:

- The electric energy use of the heat pump
- The electric energy use of the air handling units (fans)
- The electric energy use of the circulation pumps

The MPC has the following constraints:

1. min and max operative temperatures ($[22, 24]^{\circ}\text{C}$ for most zones) and max CO₂ concentration (800 ppm) for each zone that requires comfort
2. min and max supply temperatures for the TABS and floor heating circuits ($[20, 26]^{\circ}\text{C}$) and for the supply ventilation temperature ($[19, 29]^{\circ}\text{C}$)

The number of intervals of the horizon is 14. The following adaptive step size is used: $\Delta t = [0.25, 0.25, 0.5, 1, 1.75, 2.5, 4, 8, 12, 16, 28]h$. The total horizon length is thus 74.25h.

4.3. MPC preliminary results

This section describes briefly some preliminary MPC results. For an extensive description we refer to D4.11.

Figure 4-2 and Figure 4-4 show the zone temperatures from the ground floor, from level +1, +2, +3, and the CO₂ concentration of the different zones for respectively a winter and a summer period. Figure 4-3 and Figure 4-5 show the daily electrical use of the whole HVAC installation, of the heat pumps, and of the supply fan for the same periods. Note that no sensor was available to measure the electricity use of the extraction fan. All figures show additionally the daily average outdoor temperature and the MPC status. In order to determine the MPC savings, Figure 4-3 and Figure 4-5 also contain boxplots of the daily electrical use of the whole HVAC installation from the period 2018-01-01 to 2018-12-31. Each boxplot only contains data for days which had a similar daily average outdoor temperature as the plotted day.

4.3.1. Winter period

Figure 4-2 shows that the zones temperatures are within the comfortable bounds during the day during weekdays. The CO₂ concentrations sporadically exceeds its limit of 800 ppm but never for a long time. In case of MPC, this is mainly due to the coarse control interval of 15 minutes during which the MPC set points cannot change while the CO₂ concentration in small rooms such as meetings room can rise faster. Despite these sporadic high concentrations, the temperature and air quality is considered high during both when MPC is ON and OFF.

Figure 4-2: Fluvius: winter period: measured zones temperatures from Lo and from L+1,+2,+3, CO₂ concentrations, daily average outdoor temperature, and MPC status.

From Figure 4-3 one can see that when the MPC is off, the total HVAC and the heat pumps electricity use is similar to the ones from 2019 except on Sundays. While the systems was mostly off on the Sundays of 2019, the data shows that it is not the case in 2020. When MPC is ON, we can observe 22 to 42% energy savings on the total HVAC electrical use during weekdays and an increase of 14% during the considered Sunday. This is due to the fact that MPC assumes that the circulation pumps are modulating while in reality most of them in the considered building are on/off controlled. The post-processing turns them ON when MPC requests even a small modulation.

This will be improved in the near future. Despite these losses during the weekend, MPC was able to save 99 kWh/day (32%) during the considered period compared to the RBC of 2018.

The graphs of the heat pumps and of the supply fan electrical use indicates that most of savings are coming from the decrease of the ventilation and of the heat pump electrical use.

Figure 4-3: Fluvius: winter period: comparison between the current daily total HVAC (red line, upper graph), the heat pumps (red line, second graph), and the supply fan electrical (red line, third graph) uses and the ones from 2018 for a similar daily average outdoor temperature (boxplot), average outdoor temperature, MPC status.

4.3.2. Summer period

Figure 4-4 shows that the zone temperatures are within the comfortable bounds during the day during weekdays. Similarly to the winter period, the CO₂ concentrations sporadically exceeds its limit of 600 ppm (this limit has been decreased compared to the value of January 2020 due to the Corona pandemic) but never for a long time. The comfort is thus also considered high for the displayed period.

Figure 4-4: Fluvius: summer period: measured zones temperatures from Lo and from L+1,+2,+3, CO2 concentrations, daily average outdoor temperature, and MPC status.

From Figure 4-4 one can draw similar conclusions than for the winter period but with, of course, lower net energy savings (49 kWh/day (29%) on average) as the building uses less energy to cool than to heat up.

Figure 4-5: Fluvius: summer period: comparison between the current daily total HVAC (red line, upper graph), the heat pumps (red line, second graph), and the supply fan electrical (red line, third graph) uses and the ones from 2018 for a similar daily average out

4.4. Encountered difficulties

During the course of this project, we encountered many problems preventing us to keep MPC uninterruptedly ON. Beside the multiple bugs that we needed to fix in our BACnet communication framework, we encountered the following problems:

Upon request of the building owner, the MPC algorithm of Fluvius is running on a virtual machine provided by Fluvius. Several weeks of MPC controls were lost at different moments due to the virtual machine becoming inaccessible and the change of its IP-address breaking the BACnet communication.

In the Fluvius building, the installed hardware are an old generation of Priva PLCs (HX100) which did not support BACnet communication. A Priva gateway (SX100) was installed to create a BACnet interface. While the BACnet communication between MPC and the gateway works mostly fine, it gets stuck on regular basis for a still unclear reason, causing each time the automatic shutdown of MPC.

Finally, MPC also needs to be regularly shutdown due to problems with the machines such as the ventilation being turned off due to a malfunctioning fire damper (now solved) and the heat pumps going into error mode due to a water flow problem. The cause of the later is still unclear. It happens both when the original control is working and when MPC is ON.

5. Ter Potterie

This section discusses the practical MPC implementation for Ter Potterie. Section 5.1 lists the MPC optimization variables and the control variables sent to the BMS of the building, Section 5.2 describes the objective, horizon and constraints of the MPC and Section 5.3 gives some preliminary MPC results.

5.1. MPC control signals

The optimization variables of MPC and the actual control signals to the BMS are summarized in Table 5-1. For the convenience of the reader, the hydraulic scheme included in D4.7 is repeated here (Figure 5-1).

Figure 5-1: Ter Potterie: simplified hydraulic scheme

Table 5-1: Ter Potterie: MPC control signals

	Optimization variables in Model	Control signals in building	Remark
Mode	Mode	Mode	Mode is not optimized but it is defined by a weighted average outdoor temperature. When this average temperature drops below 16°C, cooling mode is activated, otherwise heating mode is used. When in cooling mode, if the heat exchanger for passive cooling delivers less than 1% of its nominal power, passive mode is activated.
AHUs	Valve opening heating coil	Supply air temperature set point	For the 12 AHUs
	Valve opening cooling coil		
	Modulation heat recovery wheel		
HVAC	Injection valve opening for each floor heating/cooling and TABS circuit	Set point temperature for supply of each floor heating/cooling and TABS circuit	-
	Heat pump modulation rate	MPC signal not used. RBC controls it	RBC defines the set punt temperature for the heat pump based on the maximum set point of circuits. MPC assumes a modulating heat pump while in reality two heat pumps with each two non-modulating compressors are installed.
	Radiator valve opening	MPC signal not used. In reality radiators have thermostatic valve	-
SUM	# optimization variables: 49	# BACnet points: 71	

The hydraulic system of Ter Potterie requires that the TABS are either connected to the heat exchanger of the passive cooling or to the heat pump. The mode is computed based on a weighted average outdoor temperature and MPC optimizes its control actions taking the mode into account.

The Modelica model contains detailed models of the Air Handling Units (AHU) including the fans, recovery unit, heating and cooling coils. The fans provide a constant mass flow with a night set back and they may not be optimized but the rest can be optimized. As the BMS already contained a well working control (after some manual tuning improvements) to track a set point supply ventilation temperature, we decided to let MPC control the set point instead of controlling each component. No loss of optimality is expected by this simplification.

Similarly, MPC optimizes the injection valve openings for the floor heating and TABS circuits and we decided to let MPC control the set point of the supply temperature of each circuit instead of the valve directly.

MPC optimizes the heat pump modulation while in reality, the heat pump control is entirely left to the original BMS. The BMS set the heat pump supply temperature set point to the maximum of the floor heating and TABS circuit supply temperature set point which boils down to the actions prescribed by MPC. Controlling the heat pump and its auxiliary systems (borefield pump, circulation pump at the condensor side, and valves) is a delicate task as the heat pump can quickly get into an error mode if the mass flow is too low. As the original BMS has proven to be correctly tuned and as the circulation pump with constant pressure head did not provide additional saving potentials, we decided to leave it untouched for the first MPC version.

Finally, the gas boiler set point temperature is not optimized as a constant temperature is required for the domestic hot water. While the valve opening of the heating coils (which are fed by the gas boiler) are optimized, the radiators are not included in the MPC model. This is because each radiator has its own thermostatic valve which is manually controllable. By leaving out the radiators, we force MPC to use the TABS, floor heating, and AHUs to achieved comfort, such that the radiators need not be used. During the heating season, the supply temperature to the radiator circuit will be decreased to limit the power of the radiators to a minimum as they are not expected to be necessary to achieve comfort anymore.

The total number of optimization variables is 49 while 71 control signals are sent to the BMS. The difference comes from the post-processing and from the fact that some set points can only be indirectly controlled (e.g. PI set point can only be controlled by overwriting its min and max value).

5.2. MPC objective, horizon, and constraints

The MPC objective considers the energy use of production and distribution devices:

- The electric energy use of the heat pump
- The electric energy use of the air handling units (fans)
- The electric energy use of the circulation pumps
- The equivalent energy use of the gas boiler

The MPC has the following constraints:

- min and max operative temperatures for each zone requiring comfort ($[22, 25]^{\circ}\text{C}$ for office rooms and $[23, 25]^{\circ}\text{C}$ for the other rooms)
- min and max supply temperatures for the TABS and floor heating circuits ($[19, 35]^{\circ}\text{C}$) and for the supply ventilation temperature ($[18, 24]^{\circ}\text{C}$ for office rooms and $[21, 24]^{\circ}\text{C}$ for the other rooms, except the cafeteria where the ventilation temperature can go up to 30°C).

The following adaptive step size is used for the horizon: $\Delta t = [0.3, 0.3, 0.3, 1, 1, 1, 2, 2, 4, 4, 8, 12, 18, 24]h$. The total horizon length is thus 78h.

5.3. MPC preliminary results

This section describes briefly some preliminary MPC results. For an extensive description we refer to D4.11.

Figure 5-2 shows the zone temperatures from the day rooms and the zone temperatures from the office and multi-functional rooms from 2020-11-01 to 2021-01-12 and Figure 5-3, Figure 5-4, and Figure 5-5 show respectively the daily electrical use of the whole HVAC installation, the daily electrical use of the heat pumps, and the daily total thermal energy use from the gas boiler (heating and domestic hot water) for the same period. All figures show additionally the daily average outdoor temperature and the MPC status. In order to determine the MPC savings, Figure 5-3 to Figure 5-5 also contain boxplots of the daily energy use from the period 2018-03-01 to 2019-12-31. Each boxplot only contains data for days which had a similar daily average outdoor temperature as the plotted day. Note that due to a wrong wire connection, the total HVAC energy use measured

in 2018 and 2019 also included the electrical energy use of the kitchen. The average electrical use of the kitchen is estimated as 73 kWh/day based on a period of three weeks. This value has been deduced from the HVAC energy use to correct it.

From Figure 5-2 one can see that the zone temperatures are mostly within their comfort bounds both during MPC and RBC operations confirming that comfort is respected.

Figure 5-2: Ter Potterie: measured zones temperatures, daily average outdoor temperature, and MPC status.

Figure 5-3 shows the electrical use of entire HVAC installation and Figure 5-4 shows the electrical use of the heat pumps. It should be noted that 60 to 80% of the total HVAC electrical energy is used by the fans of the AHU's and that those fans may not be optimized by MPC. The figures show an average electrical energy savings of 96 kWh/day for the entire HVAC and of 62 kWh/day (28%) for the heat pump.

Figure 5-5 shows the thermal energy of the gas boiler which feeds the radiators, the heating coils of the AHU's and the domestic hot water. The results are difficult to interpret as an increase of the gas use can be due to a higher use for space heating or a higher use for domestic hot water. During the MPC period, an average of 79 kWh/day extra was used compared to the reference period. Note however, that to compare this value with the energy savings on the electrical use, the later should be converted to thermal energy using a COP of 5 or higher.

Figure 5-4: Ter Potterie: comparison between the current daily heat pump electrical (red line) and the ones from 2019-2020 for a similar daily average outdoor temperature (boxplot), average outdoor temperature, MPC status.

Figure 5-5: Ter Potterie: comparison between the current daily total thermal energy use from the gas boiler (red line) and the ones from 2019-2020 for a similar daily average outdoor temperature (boxplot), average outdoor temperature, MPC status.

6. Libeznice

This section describes the practical MPC implementation for Libeznice school, Czech Republic. As stated above, for this demo building the grey-box MPC approach was applied.

Section 6.1 summarizes MPC optimization variables and the control variables sent to the BMS of the building, Section 6.2 describes the objective, horizon and constraints of the MPC and Section 6.3 gives some preliminary MPC results.

6.1. MPC control signals

The MPC in Libeznice school controls the following variables:

- desired supply water temperature to TABS (°C)
- desired supply air temperature of each AHU (°C)
- desired speed of supply fan of each AHU (%)

Together, MPC controls 19 variables. The list of all variables including corresponding MERVIS variables is stated in Table 6-1.

The output of MPC are TABS power and AHUs power, therefore some post-processing logic must be performed after each MPC calculation to obtain the control signals, which are communicated through MERVIS Scada interface with BMS.

The MPC is re-computed every 20 minutes, calculates the post-processing logic and saves the set points to MERVIS Scada interface. The post-processing logic is described in D4.10.

Due to noise at higher speed, the fans of AHUs can be operated only in range 0-60% except of AHU 9, it can be operated with the maximum speed.

Control signal	Corresponding MERVIS variable
TABS supply water temperature	ZS_Libeznice/TABS/TABS supply water temperature setpoint
AHU 1 fan speed setpoint	AHU1 - class Mercury/Required speed FCS
AHU 1 supply air temperature setpoint	AHU1 - class Mercury / Inlet air temperature setpoint FCS
AHU 2 fan speed setpoint	AHU2 - class Venus/ Required speed FCS
AHU 2 supply air temperature setpoint	AHU2 - class Venus/ Inlet air temperature setpoint FCS
AHU 3 fan speed setpoint	AHU3 - class Earth/ Required speed FCS
AHU 3 supply air temperature setpoint	AHU3 - class Earth / Inlet air temperature setpoint FCS
AHU 4 fan speed setpoint	AHU4 - class Mars/ Required speed FCS
AHU 4 supply air temperature setpoint	AHU4 - class Mars/ Inlet air temperature setpoint FCS
AHU 5 fan speed setpoint	AHU5 - class Jupiter/ Required speed FCS
AHU 5 supply air temperature setpoint	AHU5 - class Jupiter/ Inlet air temperature setpoint FCS
AHU 6 fan speed setpoint	AHU6 - class Saturn/ Required speed FCS
AHU 6 supply air temperature setpoint	AHU6 - class Saturn/ Inlet air temperature setpoint FCS
AHU 7 fan speed setpoint	AHU7 - class Uran/ Required speed FCS
AHU 7 supply air temperature setpoint	AHU7 - class Uran/ Inlet air temperature setpoint FCS
AHU 8 fan speed setpoint	AHU8 - class Neptun/ Required speed FCS

AHU 8 supply air temperature setpoint	AHU8 – class Neptun/ Inlet air temperature setpoint FCS
AHU 9 fan speed setpoint	AHU9 – hall and office/ Required speed FCS
AHU 9 supply air temperature setpoint	VZT 9 - hall and office /Inlet air temperature setpoint FCS

Table 6-1: Libeznice school: MPC control signals.

6.2. MPC objective, horizon and constraints

The MPC requirements and formulation of optimization task (objective and constraints) is also stated in D4.10.

The aim of MPC implementation at Libeznice school is to keep zone temperatures as well as CO₂ concentrations in desired ranges and minimize the delivered power to TABS and AHUs at the same time. The maximum allowed CO₂ concentration in all classes is 1000 ppm. In heating mode, the indoor temperature in all classes should be higher than 22°C for Monday-Friday 6AM-5PM and 21°C during nights and weekends. In cooling mode, the desired indoor air temperature should be 23°C all the time.

The MPC objective can be formulated as follows:

$$\min \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} |\beta_{BKT} Q_{BKT}(k)| + \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \alpha_{T,i} (T_i(k) - z_{T,i}(k)) + \alpha_{c,i} (c_i(k) - z_{C,i}) + |\beta_{v,i} Q_{v,i}(k)|$$

$$i = \{1, 2, \dots, 9\} \text{ (classrooms and hall)}$$

N is 72 samples, corresponding to sample time of the controller 20 minutes and prediction horizon 24 hours.

subject to:

$$x(k+1) = Ax(k) + Bu(k) + Vd(k) \quad (\text{linear dynamics})$$

$$x_0 = x_{init}$$

$$z_{T,i}(k) \geq T_{ref,i}(k) \text{ in heating mode, } z_{T,i}(k) \leq T_{ref,i}(k) \text{ in cooling mode}$$

$$z_{C,i} \leq C_{ref,i}$$

$$Q_{BKT,cool} \leq Q_{BKT} \leq Q_{BKT,heat}$$

$$Q_{v,cool} \leq Q_{v,i} \leq Q_{v,heat}$$

$$0 \leq \dot{m}_{v,i} \leq \max(\dot{m}_{v,max}, c_i - c_{AMB})$$

$$\beta_{BKT} = 0.001$$

$$\alpha_{T,i} = 100$$

$$\alpha_{c,i} = 0.001$$

$$\beta_{v,i} = 0.01$$

where:

T_i is the temperature in the i -th classroom, c_i is the CO₂ concentration in the i -th classroom, $z_{T,i}$ and $z_{C,i}$ are the corresponding slack variables, Q_{BKT} is the heating/cooling power delivered to TABS, $Q_{v,i}$ is the heating/cooling power delivered to individual AHUs, $T_{ref,i}$ is the minimum desired, respectively maximum allowed classroom temperature, $C_{ref,i}$ is the maximum allowed CO₂ concentration, $Q_{BKT,heat}$ is the maximum heating TABS power 40 kW, $Q_{BKT,cool}$ is the maximum cooling TABS power 30 kW, $Q_{v,heat}$ is the maximum heating power of each AHU 500W, $Q_{v,cool}$ is the maximum cooling power of each AHU 500W, $\dot{m}_{v,i}$ is the mass flow rate of air in the i -th AHU, $\dot{m}_{v,max}$ is the maximum possible mass flow rate in AHU 390 kg/s and c_{AMB} is the ambient CO₂ concentration 300 ppm.

6.3. Preliminary results

The new MPC implementation in Libeznice school was put into operation on 15th October 2018. The main changes compared to the old MPC implementation are:

- MPC controls both TABS and ventilation system (previous MPC implementation controlled only TABS while the ventilation was controlled via independent rule-based control (RBC))
- Grey-box temperature and CO₂ model was implemented for each class

As can be seen in Figure 6-1., the first results show that the classroom temperatures are maintained within the bounds 21°C – 24°C in winter (heating) season. The MPC setpoint in winter season is 22°C with the night and weekend setback 21°C.

Figure 6-1: Measured temperatures in each classroom and their comfort bounds controlled by new MPC implementation in winter.

As the school is also operated during the summer holidays as a center for summer camps, it makes sense to evaluate thermal comfort in summer season too. As can be seen in Figure 6-2, the classroom temperatures are maintained in the bounds 22-24°C, however they exceed 24°C in June where there are high solar and occupancy gains. Moreover, the ambient temperature in June exceeds 30°C and MPC operates TABS with the maximum power. During summer camps in July and August the classroom temperatures are maintained more often in the comfort bounds (excluding periods with heat pump problems) as there are less children (lower occupancy gains) compared to the normal school year.

Figure 6-2: Measured temperatures in each classroom controlled by MPC in summer.

The TABS energy and electrical consumption of AHUs with respect to IAQ are evaluated as the primary results of new MPC implementation. The TABS energy with respect to the ambient and classroom temperatures is evaluated separately for heating and cooling season. The evaluation for heating season is shown in Table 6-2. The TABS energy was recalculated using historical data and then the linear regression (TABS daily energy in dependence of daily average temperature) to the same ambient temperature during the old MPC implementation.

It can be seen that the TABS energy is slightly higher for new MPC, however the average classroom temperature is much closer to setpoint 22°C, thus the new MPC implementation improves the thermal comfort during the heating season. This fact confirms also the feedback from teachers in Libeznice school. They acknowledged higher air quality thanks to the integration of AHUs into the new MPC implementation.

Table 6-3 shows the evaluation for summer (cooling) season. As can be shown, the average ambient temperature for old and new MPC is comparable (approx. 23.8 °C). Table 6-3 shows that the building is operated with lower TABS energy when using new MPC (approx. 4% savings of TABS energy), while keeping the same thermal comfort (average classroom temperatures is approx. 23.5 °C).

The electrical consumption of AHUs is not directly measured, but it can be calculated using fan speed (which is measured). There are 9 independent AHUs and two fans in each AHU (supply and extraction fan) both with the nominal electrical power 340 W. The fan power is directly proportional to the cube of fan speed.

The comparison of electrical consumption of AHU with rule-based control (RBC) and new MPC implementation is in Table 6-4 and the evaluation of IAQ in all classrooms is shown in Table 6-5. Since the AHUs were equipped with the sensors (speed, temperature, CO₂ sensors) at the end of April 2018 and new MPC implementation was started at the end of October 2018, only 4 months – May, June, September, October 2018 (excluding summer holidays) can be compared with the new MPC implementation. The same months, but one year after (2019) are therefore considered for the new MPC implementation.

As can be seen in Table 6-4, the electrical consumption of AHU with the new MPC implementation (1217 kWh) is slightly higher than RBC (1017 kWh), about 14%. The AHUs were not controlled with the old MPC implementation, as they were controlled via independent rule-based control where the fan speed was set on the constant value (about 30%) including nights and weekends. The new MPC controls fans of AHU with about twice higher speed (the maximum allowed speed is 60% due to the noise) than the rule-based control in order to ensure the desired IAQ (CO₂ concentration). The electrical consumption of 09-Hall AHU is much higher than the other AHUs, because for this AHU the fans can be operated with 100% of speed. There were some technical problems

with the AHU o8-Neptune during the new MPC, therefore this AHU was operated with lower speed compared to the other AHUs.

Table 6-5 compares the average CO₂ concentration in individual classrooms before and after the new MPC deployment. Moreover, the CO₂ concentration is evaluated only within the school days (Monday to Friday) and from 7AM to 4PM when the school is considered to be occupied. As can be seen, in all classrooms, except of o8-Neptune, is the concentration lower talking about the new MPC implementation (reduction in average of 8%).

Table 6-2: Preliminary results of new MPC implementation during heating season.

	TABS energy (kWh)		Ambient temperature (°C)		Classroom temperature (°C)	
	old MPC	new MPC	new MPC		old MPC	new MPC
November	209.7	179.7	6.3		23.2	22.9
December	219.8	249.9	4.6		23.0	22.5
January	266.0	290.2	1.8		23.1	22.4
February	189.8	203.0	4.2		22.8	22.6
Total	885.3	922.7	4.3		23.0	22.6

Table 6-3: Preliminary results of new MPC implementation in summer.

	TABS energy (kWh)		Ambient temperature (°C)		Classroom temperature (°C)	
	old MPC	new MPC	old MPC	new MPC	old MPC	new MPC
June	270.3	335.4	22.0	25.2	24.1	23.8
July	306.3	244.3	24.6	23.5	23.2	23.6
August	251.7	209.9	24.7	22.7	23.1	22.9
Total	828.3	789.6	23.8	23.8	23.5	23.5

Table 6-4: Comparison of electrical consumption of AHUs for RBC and new MPC implementation.

	Electrical consumption of AHU (kWh), RBC (May, Jun, Sep, Oct 2018)	Electrical consumption of AHU (kWh), new MPC (May, Jun, Sep, Oct 2019)
01-Mercury	50	66
02-Venus	32	62
03-Earth	50	63
04-Mars	40	69
05-Jupiter	60	68
06-Saturn	66	69
07-Uranus	62	69
08-Neptune	63	34
09-Hall	647	717
sum	1070	1217

Table 6-5: Average CO₂ concentrations in all classrooms with old and new MPC implementation.

classroom	old MPC (May, Jun, Sep, Oct 2018)	new MPC (May, Jun, Sep, Oct 2019)
01-Mercury	844	793
02-Venus	626	519
03-Earth	786	696
04-Mars	865	744
05-Jupiter	764	710
06-Saturn	720	718
07-Uranus	810	729
08-Neptune	671	682
average	761	699

7. Solarwind

This section discusses the practical MPC implementation for Solarwind. Section 7.1 lists the MPC optimization variables and the control variables sent to the BMS of the building, Section 7.2 describes the objective, horizon and constraints of the MPC and Section 7.3 gives some preliminary MPC results.

7.1. MPC control signals

The optimization variables of MPC and the actual control signals sent to the BMS are summarized Table 7-1. For the convenience of the reader, the hydraulic scheme included in D4.7 is repeated here (Figure 7-1).

Figure 7-1: Solarwind: simplified hydraulic scheme

Table 7-1: Solarwind: MPC control signals in model and actual control signals to the Building Management System

	Optimization variables in model	Actual control signals to BMS	Remarks
AHU	Supply bypass opening	Supply temperature	6 AHUs
	Return bypass opening		6 AHUs
	Three-way valve opening of heating coil		6 AHUs
	Pump pressure head of heating coil		6 AHUs
	Heat pump modulation		6 AHUs
	Indirect evaporative cooling humidity increase		4 AHUs
	Humidifier modulation	Supply absolute humidity	4 AHUs
	Pressure head supply fan	Pressure head supply fan	6 AHUs
	Pressure head return fan	Pressure head return fan	6 AHUs
Vent	Two-way valve opening of re-heating coils	Supply air temperature set point	64 re-heating coils
	Opening VAV supply and return	Opening VAV supply and return	64 x 2 VAVs The same signals is used for the supply and return VAV.
HYDRO	Three-way valve opening of AHU heating coil circuit	Supply water temperature set point	-
	Pump pressure head of AHU heating coil circuit	Postprocessing: on/off	-
	Three-way valve opening of VAV heating coil circuit	Supply water temperature set point	-
	Pump pressure head of VAV heating coil circuit	Postprocessing: on/off	-
	Three-way valve opening of TABS supply circuit	Supply water temperature set point	North & south supply circuits
	Pump pressure head of TABS supply circuit	Postprocessing: on/off	North & south supply circuits
	Two-way valve opening of TABS circuits	Two-way valve opening of TABS circuits	18 north & 11 south circuits

	Three-way valve opening of radiant ceiling circuit	Supply water temperature set point	-
	Pump pressure head of radiant ceiling circuit	Postprocessing: on/off	-
	Two-way valve opening of radiant ceiling circuits	Two-way valve opening of radiant ceiling circuits	8 circuits
	Two-way valves opening for heating or cooling	Two-way valves opening for heating or cooling	North TABS, south TABS, radiant ceilings
Production	Set point temperature of heat pump	Set point temperature of heat pump	-
	Pump supply pressures and valve positions for solar collector and pellet boiler	Set point temperature of hot water storage tank	
SUM	# optimization variables: 217	# BACnet points: 265	

The air handling units contain fans, indirect evaporative cooling heat exchangers, a heat recovery heat pump, a heating coil and a humidifier to passively and actively condition the supply air. Control signals for each device are determined internally in the AHU, based on temperature and humidity setpoints for the supply air, and two pressure setpoints.

The conditioned air is distributed to 64 pairs of VAVs (supply and return), each containing a re-heating coil before the air is distributed into the zones. MPC optimizes and sets the VAV damper opening and communicates the heating coil supply air temperature set point to the existing PI controller.

MPC can heat or cool the zones using the TABS. Groups of zones are connected to TABS circuits, each being controlled by one two-way valve. Those circuits are connected to one of two distribution circuits in the building. Each circuit (north and south) has independent temperature using a three-way valve and pressure control using a pump.

The eight zones on the top floor have a radiant ceiling, each controlled by two-way valve. The supply water temperature to all zones is controlled using a three-way valve.

The three-way valves of the north and south TABS and radiant ceiling circuits are connected to a separate collector. The collector is connected either to the heat production circuit or to the geothermal cooling circuit. The supply temperature of the heat pump is optimized. Other production instances like the solar thermal collector, the pellet boiler, circulation pumps are optimized but are not controlled directly. Instead a temperature set point for the hot water storage tank is provided.

7.2. MPC objective, horizon, and constraints

The MPC objective considers the energy use of production and distribution devices:

- The electric energy use of the heat pump
- The electric energy use of the air handling units (fans, pumps, heat pump)
- The electric energy use of the circulation pumps
- The equivalent energy use of the pellet boiler (scaling factor 1/3)

The MPC has the following constraints:

- Constraint on the heat pump maximum supply temperature
- Constraint on the buffer tank water temperature
- Constraint on the AHU supply air temperatures
- Constraint on the supply air temperatures in the zones (after the reheating coils) ([16,26]°C)
- Constraint on the TABS supply water temperatures
- Constraint on zone temperatures (the setpoints are chosen by the users and may change over time)
- Constraint on zone CO₂ concentrations

The optimization horizon consists of 13 intervals. Following adaptive step size is used: 1/4, 1/4, 3/4, 2, 3, 6, 6, 6, 6, 6, 6, 6h, which adds up to a total horizon of 2.26 days.

7.3. MPC preliminary results

The MPC model has been used in standalone optimizations to test the correct operation. Twelve optimizations with a horizon of 1 month have been run for which results are presented at the NMPC conference of July 2021 [4]. The paper lists a number of strengths of white-box NMPC for building HVAC applications and illustrates them using the Solarwind MPC results.

The practical implementation of the MPC is ongoing at the time of writing. To implement and test a custom communication layer using XML, and to verify proper operation before controlling the whole building, a phased approach is chosen. Following phases are identified and agreed with the building owner:

1. MPC running in the background without writing its control actions to test the stability of the algorithm (from 15/12 to 18/01/2021)
2. Control the VAV opening and setpoint temperatures of 3 zones on the 3rd floor (from 18/01 to 26/01/2021).
3. Additionally, Control the AHU, VAV's and radiant ceilings on the 4th floor.
4. Controlling the whole building.

At the time of writing phase 2 is ongoing. Communication issues regarding the AHU set points are being resolved together with the building control responsible.

7.4. Encountered difficulties

In the contrary to the other white-box MPCs, the MPC of Solarwind does not communicate directly through BACnet but through a XML middle layer developed by the control company (DRC Technology). We are currently experiencing some problems to write our setpoints to the AHU's and we are currently working on a solution together with the company. It is still too early to list other encountered problems.

8. Nathan

This section discusses the MPC design for the Nathan headquarters building. Section 8.1 lists the MPC optimization variables and the control variables sent to the BMS of the building, Section 8.2 describes the objective, horizon and constraints of the MPC and Section 8.3 gives some preliminary MPC results based on simulations.

Notice that Nathan is not a demonstration building. The MPC development for this building is meant as an exercise to quantify the time required to develop an MPC using the latest version of our tools. This time estimates is used to evaluate its commercialization potential. For more information, see D3.3.

8.1. Building description

Nathan’s building is an office building of 3000 m² connected to a production hall of 2000 m² (see Figure 8-1) and located in Zevenaar, Netherlands. It is a well-insulated, highly glazed building. Heat and cold are produced by an Aquifer Thermal Energy Storage (ATES) system connected to two heat pumps and a heat exchanger. The hot and cold water is distributed to six-way valves of the 16 TABS circuits of which the pipes are integrated both in the floor and in the ceiling and floor heating for the production hall. Most of the zones are furthermore equipped with VAVs and re-heating coils connected to three air handling units with recovery wheel and change-over coil. A special feature of the building is that the ducts are integrated into the concrete of the floors.

Figure 8-1: Nathan: building (www.nathan.nl)

8.2. MPC control signals

The optimization variables of MPC and the actual control signals sent to the BMS are summarized in Table 8-1. For the convenience of the reader, the hydraulic scheme is given in Figure 8-2.

Figure 8-2: Nathan: simplified hydraulic scheme

Table 8-1: Nathan: MPC control signals in model and actual control signals to the Building Management System

	Optimization variables in model	Control signals in building	Remark
AHU (x 3)	Valve opening heating, valve opening cooling change-over coil (equivalent to six-way valve)	Supply ventilation set point	-
	Pressure head pump for coil		-
	Modulation heat recovery wheel		-
	Pressure head supply fan	Pressure head supply fan and return fan	-
Vent	Two-way valve opening re-heating coils	Supply ventilation set point	59 re-heating coils but 1 set point per zone --> 26 set points
	Opening VAV supply	VAV flow	59 VAVs but 1 MPC control variable per zone --> 26 optimization variables
HYDRO	Six-way valve position for TABS and FH circuits	Supply temperature set point for heating and cooling mode	16 TABS and FH circuits
	Pressure head pump P1 and P2 (for hot and cold main collectors)	Pressure head pump P1 and P2 (for hot and cold main collectors)	-
	Heat pump modulation rate, pressure head pumps for heat pump	Temperature set point for hot storage tank	-
	Pressure head pumps for heat exchanger	Temperature set point for cold storage tank	-
SUM	# optimization variables: 89	# BACnet points: 282	

The Modelica model contains detailed models of the three Air Handling Units (AHU) including the fans, recovery unit, heating and cooling coils. MPC optimizes the supply fan power and the flow through each VAV. The return fan power is chosen to get a balanced ventilation. This is necessary as the VAVs are only installed on the supply and not on the return air. Additionally, MPC prescribes the ventilation supply temperature set point for each re-heating coil. As the BMS already contained a well working control to track a set point supply ventilation temperature, both at the AHU level and at the re-heating coil level, we decided to let MPC control the set points instead of controlling each component. No loss of optimality is expected by this simplification.

Similarly, MPC optimizes the six-way valve openings for the floor heating and TABS circuits and we decided to let MPC control the set point of the supply temperature of each circuit instead of the valve directly.

MPC optimizes the heat pump modulation and the pumps of the passive heat exchanger while in reality, the control of these components are entirely left to the original BMS. Instead MPC sends a temperature set point for the hot and the cold storage tank. This was requested by the installer. The control of the ATES system is also left untouched as it has its own control system which is independent of the BMS.

The total number of optimization variables is 89 while 282 control signals are sent to the BMS. The difference comes from the post-processing and from the fact that some set points can only be indirectly controlled (e.g. PI set point can only be controlled by overwriting its min and max value).

8.3. MPC objective, horizon, and constraints

The MPC objective considers the energy use of production and distribution devices:

- The electric energy use of the heat pump
- The electric energy use of the air handling units (fans, pumps)
- The electric energy use of the circulation pumps

The MPC has the following constraints:

- Constraint on the heat pump maximum supply temperature
- Constraint on the AHU supply air temperatures
- Constraint on the supply air temperatures in the zones (after the reheating coils)
- Constraint on the TABS supply water temperatures
- Constraint on zone temperatures
- Constraint on zone CO₂ concentrations

The optimization horizon consists of 13 intervals. Following adaptive step size is used: 1/4, 1/4, 3/4, 2, 3, 6, 6, 6, 6, 6, 6, 6h, which adds up to a total horizon of 2.26 days.

8.4. MPC preliminary results

The MPC model has been used in standalone optimizations to test the correct operation. Three optimizations with a horizon of 1 month (January, March, April) have been run and the results are presented here below.

Figure 8-2, Figure 8-3 and Figure 8-4 illustrate the results obtained by MPC for the month of January, April, and August. Each graph shows i) the zone temperatures, ii) the zone CO₂ concentrations, iii) the AHU flows, iv) the heat supplied to each TABS (negative values indicate cooling), v) the valve position of the re-heating coils, vi) the heat delivered by the heat pump, the cold delivered by the heat exchanger, and the sum of the TABS heat, vii) the heat pump supply temperature and the AHUs supply temperatures, and viii) the outdoor temperature.

The comfort bounds for the simulations are [22, 24]°C for the zone temperatures and 800 ppm for the CO₂ concentrations, 24/7. For the real MPC implementation, we will propose to the building owner to relax the comfort bounds during the night to follow a similar schedule to the ventilation which is turned off during the night and during weekends. The ventilation supply temperature at the AHU level is constrained between 16 and 23°C but the re-heating coil can heat it further up to 28°C. During the night, the AHU is turned off and the temperature drops but without affecting the zone as there is no flow.

The figures show a good thermal and CO₂ comfort in each simulated month.

Figure 8-2 shows that the building needs heat but no cooling during January except on rare occasions. On those days where a small amount of cooling is necessary to meet the stringent comfort bound of 24°C, some zones are at their upper comfort limit while others are at their lower comfort limit. Also note that on those days, the valves of some re-heating coils are fully open. Further reducing the ventilation supply temperature at the AHU level would probably lead to discomfort in some zones and MPC therefore needs to cool with TABS. Slightly relaxing the comfort bound would help to remove those cooling needs. In contrast, during the month of April and August, Figure 8-3 and Figure 8-4 show that very little heating is required. TABS are only used to cool while the little required heating power is systematically provided by the re-heating coils. Note however that the reheating coils can only heat when the pump P2 is on (not plotted), so the valve position of the re-heating coil should not be confused with the heating power that they supply. The small mismatch between the *geothermal cooling power*

and the *TABS Tot Power* in Figure 8-4 indicates that the change-over coils of the AHU are sometimes used for cooling but significantly less than cooling with TABS.

Figure 8-3: Nathan: MPC simulation results for January

Figure 8-4: Nathan: MPC simulation results for April

Figure 8-5: Nathan: MPC simulation results for August

9. Conclusion

In this project, five MPCs have been successfully developed. The MPCs of the Fluvius, the Ter Potterie, and the Libeznice buildings are currently controlling the buildings, each saving energy and improving the comfort. MPC of the Solarwind building has been tested extensively in simulations and it is currently deployed. Finally, MPC of the Nathan has been tested extensively in simulations and the deployment will be discussed with the building owner after this project.

During this project and in parallel to other KU Leuven projects the white-box toolchain has been largely extended, making it possible to develop accurate non-linear white-box MPCs based on models with more than 1000 states and hundreds of optimization variables while keeping the development time to a few days (see D3.3). Those MPCs proved to produce accurate results both in simulations and in real life operations. The grey-box framework was also extended to include ventilation and not only TABS and the robustness of the control was shown by its continuous operation throughout the entire project.

Beside the MPC toolchain, KU Leuven developed its own framework for the communication between MPC and the machines during this project. It is based on the open-source python library *bacpypes*⁵ for the BACnet communication and on cronjobs in a Linux environment to schedule and perform the different tasks. EK used instead the commercial software Mervis and its convenient API.

While the different MPCs are stable and rarely fail to converge, the MPC ON-time is still rather low for the white-box MPCs. This is due to a multitude of IT, BACnet communication, and hardware problems as described in the sections below as well as the high number of variables controlled by MPC. While some problems are unavoidable and are typical to aging buildings, more development is necessary to improve the robustness of the framework.

⁵ <https://github.com/JoelBender/bacpypes>

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